

Neutrosophic α -Volterra Spaces

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Abstract: In this paper, we give some concepts concerning Neutrosophic resolvable, Neutrosophic irresolvable, Neutrosophic Volterra spaces. Then we introduce the concepts of Neutrosophic α -resolvable, Neutrosophic α -irresolvable, Neutrosophic α -Volterra spaces and also we investigated several characterizations of Neutrosophic α -Volterra spaces. Further we investigated the relation between Neutrosophic α -Volterra spaces and different kind of Neutrosophic Baire Spaces. Here we have included several examples to illustrate the concepts.

Keywords: *Neutrosophic α -Baire spaces, Neutrosophic αG_δ -set, Neutrosophic αF_σ -set, Neutrosophic α -residual, Neutrosophic α -resolvable, Neutrosophic α -irresolvable, Neutrosophic α -Volterra spaces*

1. Introduction

The concept of Neutrosophic sets and Neutrosophic set operations were first introduced by L.A. Zadeh in his classical paper [17] in the year 1965. Thereafter the paper of C.L. Chang [1] in 1968 paved the way for the subsequent tremendous growth of the numerous Neutrosophic topological concepts. The concepts of Volterra spaces have been studied extensively in classical topology in [4], [5], [6], [7] and [8]. The concept of Volterra spaces in Neutrosophic setting was introduced and studied by the authors in [13]. The concept of Intuitionistic Neutrosophic Volterra spaces was introduced and studied by Soundararajan, Rizwan and Syed Tahir Hussainy [12]. The concepts of Neutrosophic logic and Neutrosophic set were introduced by F. Smarandache [10], [11]. Afterwards, the works of Smarandache inspired A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi [9] to introduce and study the concepts of Neutrosophic crisp set and Neutrosophic crisp topological spaces. The Basic definitions and Proposition related to Neut.T.Spaces was introduced and discussed by Dhavaseelan et al. [2]. The concepts of Neutrosophic Baire spaces are introduced by R. Dhavaseelan, S. Jafari, R. Narmada Devi, Md. Hanif Page [3]. The idea of Neutrosophic α -Baire spaces are introduced by R. Vijayalakshmi, S. Anjalmoose, A. Savitha Mary [15]. The concept of Neutrosophic Semi Volterra Spaces are introduced by R. Vijayalakshmi, A. Savitha Mary, S. Anjalmoose [16]

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 [3] A Neutrosophic Topology (briefly Neut Topology) on a nonempty set X is a family N_T of Neutrosophic sets (briefly Ne.S) in X satisfying the following axioms:

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in N_T$,
- (ii) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in T$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in N_T$.
- (iii) $\bigcup G_i$ for arbitrary family $\{G_i | i \in \Lambda\}$.

In this case the ordered pair (X, N_T) or simply X is called a Neutrosophic Topological Space (briefly Ne.T.S) and each Neutrosophic set in T is called a Neutrosophic open set (briefly Ne.O.S). The complement A of a NOS A in X is called a Neutrosophic closed set (briefly Ne.C.S) in X .

Definition 2.2 [3] Let A be a Neutrosophic set in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) . Then

$Nint(P) = \bigcup \{G | G \text{ is neutrosophic open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq P\}$ is called the Neut interior of P ;

$Ncl(P) = \bigcap \{G | G \text{ is neutrosophic closed set in } X \text{ and } G \supseteq P\}$ is called the Neut closure of P
 For any Neut set A in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) it is easy to see that $1 - Ncl(P) = Nint(1 - P)$ and $1 - Nint(P) = Ncl(1 - P)$.

Definition 2.3[15] A Neut set K in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is said to a Neut α -Open set if $K \subseteq Nint(Ncl(Nint(K)))$ and Neut α -Closed set (NSCS) if $Ncl(Nint(Ncl(K))) \supseteq K$

Definition 2.4[15] Let A be a Neut set in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) . Then

$Na_{int}(P) = \bigcup \{G | G \text{ is neutrosophic } \alpha - \text{open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq P\}$ is called the Neut interior of P ;

$Na_{cl}(P) = \bigcap \{G | G \text{ is neutrosophic } \alpha - \text{closed set in } X \text{ and } G \supseteq P\}$ is called the Neut closure of P ;

Result: 2.1 Let P be a Neut set in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) . Then

$$Na_{cl}(P) = P \cup Ncl(Nint(Ncl(P)))$$

$$Na_{int}(P) = P \cap Nint(Ncl(Nint(P)))$$

Definition:2.5[15] A Neut set P in Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called Neut α -dense if there exist no Neut α -Closed set Q in (X, N_T) such that $P \subset Q \subset 1_N$. That is $Na_{cl}(P) = 1_N$

Definition 2.6[15] A Neut set P in Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called Neut α -nowhere dense (briefly N.Dense) if there exist no non-zero Neut α -open set Q in (X, N_T) such that $Q \subset Na_{cl}(P)$. That is $Na_{int}(Na_{cl}(P)) = 0_N$.

Definition 2.7:[15] Let (X, N_T) be a Neut.T.Space. A Neut set P in (X, N_T) is called Neut α -first category if $P = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i$ where P_i 's are Neut α -N.Dense sets in (X, N_T) .

Definition 2.8[15] Let (X, N_T) be a Ne.T.S. Then (X, N_T) is called a Neut α -Baire space if

$$N\alpha \text{int} \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i \right) = 0_N, \text{ where } P_i \text{'s are Neut } \alpha\text{-N.Dense sets in } (X, N_T).$$

Definition 2.9: Let P be a Neut α -first category set in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) . Then $1 - P$ is called a Neut α -residual set in (X, T) .

Proposition 2.1[15] Let (X, N_T) be a Neut.T.Space in (X, N_T) then every Neut N.Dense set is Neut α -N.Dense set in (X, N_T) .

Definition 2.10[16] A Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called a Neut Volterra space if $Ncl(\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (P_i)) = 1_N$, where P_i 's are Neut dense and Neut G_δ sets in (X, N_T)

Definition 2.11 A Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called Neut resolvable if there exists a Neut α -dense set P in (X, N_T) such that $Ncl(\bar{P}) = 1_N$. Otherwise (X, N_T) is called Neut irresolvable.

Definition 2.12 A Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called a Neut sub-maximal space if for each Neut set P in (X, N_T) , $Ncl(P) = 1_N$.

Proposition 2.2 Every Neut open sets in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) are Neut α -open in (X, N_T)

Proposition 2.3 Let (X, N_T) be a Ne.T.S. A Neut set P is a Neut dense and Ne.O.S in (X, N_T) then $1 - P$ is a Neut α -N.Dense set in (X, N_T) .

Proof: Since, P is a Neut dense set in (X, T) . We have $Ncl(P) = 1_N$. Also, since P is a Ne.O.S so $N \text{int}(P) = P$, we know that every Ne.O.S is Neut α -open set in (X, N_T) this implies $N\alpha \text{int}(P) = P$. Now $N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(1 - P)) = 1 - N\alpha cl((N\alpha \text{int}(P))) = 1 - N\alpha cl((P)) = 1 - 1 = 0$. Hence, $1 - P$ is an Neut α -N.Dense set in (X, N_T)

Proposition 2.4 In a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) a Neut set P is Neut α -N.Dense if and only if $1 - P$ is a Neut α -dense in (X, N_T) .

Proof: Let P be a Neut α -N.Dense set in (X, N_T) then $N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(P)) = 0_N$. That is, $1 - N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(P)) = 1_N$. This implies $N\alpha cl(N\alpha \text{int}(1 - P)) = 1_N$. Here $1 - P$ is α -open, since P is α -closed. So that $N\alpha cl(1 - P) = 1_N$. Hence, $1 - P$ is a Neut α -dense in (X, N_T)

3. Neutrosophic α -Volterra Spaces

Definition 3.1 A Neut set P in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called a Neut αG_δ -set in (X, N_T) if $P = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i$ where P_i 's are Neut α -open for all $i \in I$.

Definition 3.2 A Neut set P in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called a Neut αF_σ -set in (X, N_T) if $P = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i$ where P_i 's are Neut α -closed for all $i \in I$.

Definition 3.3 A Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called a Neut α -Volterra space if $N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty}(P_i))=1_N$, where P_i 's are Neut α -dense and Neut αG_{δ} sets in (X, τ) .

Definition 3.4 A Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called Neut α -resolvable if there exists a Neut α -dense set P in (X, N_T) such that $N\alpha cl(\bar{P}) = 1_N$. Otherwise (X, N_T) is called Neut α -irresolvable.

Definition 3.5 A Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called a Neut α -submaximal space if for each Neut set P in (X, N_T) , $N\alpha cl(P) = 1_N$.

Proposition 3.1 Every Neut G_{δ} sets in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) are Neut αG_{δ} -sets and the converse need not be true.

Proposition 3.2 Every Neut F_{σ} sets in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) are Neut αF_{σ} -sets and the converse need not be true.

Proposition 3.4 If the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is a Neut Baire space and the Neut N.Dense sets in (X, N_T) are Neut F_{σ} -sets in (X, N_T) then (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Baire space.

Proof: Let the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is a Neut Baire space. Then $N \text{int}\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i\right) = 0_N$, where P_i 's are Neut N.Dense sets in (X, τ) . By **Proposition 2.1**, every Neut N.Dense set is Neut α -N.Dense set in (X, N_T) . So $N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(P)) = 0_N$. By **Proposition 3.2**, every Neut F_{σ} sets in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) are Neut αF_{σ} -sets. So that $P = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i$ where P_i 's are Neut α -closed for all $i \in I$. That is $N\alpha cl(P_i) = A_i$. Since from the hypothesis the Neut α -N.Dense sets in (X, N_T) are Neut αF_{σ} -sets in (X, N_T) so that $N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(P)) = N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i)) = N\alpha \text{int}(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i)$ which implies $N\alpha \text{int}\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} P_i\right) = 0_N$, where P_i 's are Neut α - N.Dense sets in (X, N_T) . Hence (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Baire space.

Proposition 3.5 If Q is a Neut α -dense set and Neut αG_{δ} -sets in the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) then $1 - Q$ is a Neut α -first category set in (X, N_T) .

Proof: Let Q be a Neut α -dense and Neut αG_{δ} -set in (X, N_T) . Then $Q = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} Q_i$, where Q_i are α -open. Since Q is a Neut α -dense set in (X, N_T) , $N\alpha cl(Q) = 1_N$. Then $N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} Q_i) = 1_N$. But $N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} Q_i) \subseteq \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} N\alpha cl(Q_i)$. Here $1_N \subseteq \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} N\alpha cl(Q_i)$. That is $\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} N\alpha cl(Q_i) = 1_N$. Then we have $N\alpha cl(Q_i) = 1_N$ for all α -open sets Q_i so $N\alpha \text{int}(Q_i) = Q_i$ which implies that $(N\alpha cl(N\alpha \text{int}(Q_i))) = N\alpha cl(Q_i) = 1_N$ Hence $1 - (N\alpha cl(N\alpha \text{int}(Q_i))) = 0_N$

$\Rightarrow N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(1 - Q_i)) = 0_N, \forall i$. Therefore $1 - Q_i$ is a Neut α -N.Dense set in (X, N_T) . Here

$1 - Q = 1 - \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} Q_i = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} 1 - Q_i$. Therefore $1 - Q = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} 1 - Q_i$ where are Neut α -N.Dense sets in (X, N_T) .

Hence $1 - Q_i$'s a Neut α -first category set in (X, N_T) .

Example 3.1: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the Neut set Q, R, S and T on X as follows:

$$Q = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.3}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$R = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.6}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.4}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$S = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.7}, \frac{c}{0.5}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$T = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.3}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.3}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.7}, \frac{c}{0.7}\right) \right\rangle$$

Then the family $N_T = \{0_N, 1_N, Q, R\}$ is Neut Topology on X . Thus (X, N_T) is a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) . Now the sets Q and R are Neut α -dense set and $[Q \cap R = Q]$ is αG_δ then \bar{Q} is Neut α -first category set in (X, N_T)

Proposition 3.6 If A is a Neut α -N.Dense set and Neut αF_σ -sets in the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) , then $1 - A$ is a Neut α -second category set in (X, N_T) .

Example 3.2: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the Neut set Q, R, S and T on X as follows:

$$Q = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.3}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$R = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.6}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.4}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$S = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.7}, \frac{c}{0.5}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$T = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.3}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.3}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.7}, \frac{c}{0.7}\right) \right\rangle$$

Then the family $N_T = \{0_N, 1_N, Q, R\}$ is Neut topology on X . Thus (X, N_T) is a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) . Now the sets \bar{Q}, \bar{R} are Neut α -N.Dense set and $[\bar{Q} \cup \bar{R}] = \bar{R}$ is Neut F_σ -set then R is a Neut α -second category set in (X, N_T)

Proposition 3.7 If every Neut αG_δ -set is a Neut α -dense set in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) then only the Neut α -Baire space, will be a Neut α -Volterra space

Proof: Let P_i 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) be a Neut α -dense and Neut αG_δ -set in (X, N_T) .

Consider the Neut set $N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^N (P_i))$. Now $1 - N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^N (P_i)) = N\alpha \text{int}(1 - \bigcap_{i=1}^N (P_i))$

$$= N\alpha \text{int}(\bigcup_{i=1}^N (1 - P_i)). \text{ But } N\alpha \text{int}(\bigcup_{i=1}^N (1 - P_i)) \subseteq N\alpha \text{int}(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 - P_i)) \text{-----} \rightarrow (1)$$

By the **Proposition 2.3**, $1 - P_i$'s are Neut α -N.Dense sets in (X, T) . Also since (X, N_T) is a Neut

$$\alpha\text{-Baire space } N\alpha \text{int}(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 - P_i)) = 0_N \text{-----} \rightarrow (2)$$

Hence, from (1) and (2), we have $N\alpha \text{int}(\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 - P_i)) = 0_N$. Then $N\alpha \text{int}(1 - \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (P_i)) = 0_N$ implies that

$1 - N\alpha \text{cl}(\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (P_i)) = 0_N$. Then we have $N\alpha \text{cl}(\bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} (P_i)) = 1_N$. Hence (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra

space.

Example 3.3: Let $X = \{p, q\}$. Define the Neut set M, N and O on X as follows:

$$M = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.2}, \frac{q}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{p}{0.2}, \frac{q}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.6}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$N = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.6}, \frac{q}{0.2}\right), \left(\frac{p}{0.6}, \frac{q}{0.2}\right), \left(\frac{p}{0.3}, \frac{q}{0.4}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$O = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.3}, \frac{q}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{p}{0.3}, \frac{q}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.4}\right) \right\rangle$$

Then the family $N_T = \{0_N, 1_N, M, N, M \cup N\}$ is Neut topology on X . Thus (X, N_T) is a Ne.T.S.

Now $M, N, M \cup N$ are α -open sets and A is αG_δ -set in (X, N_T) . But $N\alpha \text{cl}(M) \neq 1_N$ so the Neut αG_δ is not a Neut α -dense set in (X, N_T) . Hence the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is not a Neut α -Volterra space.

Proposition 3.8: Any Neut Volterra space will be a Neut α -Volterra space.

Proof: Example 3.4: Let $X = \{a, b\}$. Define the Neut set E, F, G, H and K on X as follows:

$$E = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.7}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.5}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.9}, \frac{b}{0.3}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$F = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.8}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.8}, \frac{b}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.3}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$G = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.6}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.34}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.9}, \frac{b}{0.4}\right) \right\rangle$$

$$H = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.8}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.4}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.6}\right) \right\rangle$$

and $K = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0.7}\right), \left(\frac{a}{1}, \frac{b}{0.3}\right), \left(\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.6}\right) \right\rangle$

Then the family $N_T = \{0_N, 1_N, E, F, G, H, E \cup F, F \cap F\}$ is Neut topology on X. Thus (X, N_T) is a Ne.T.S.

Neut Open Sets = $\{E, F, G, H, E \cup F, E \cap F\}$ and

Neut Closed Sets = $\{\bar{E}, \bar{F}, \bar{G}, \bar{H}, \overline{E \cup F}, \overline{E \cap F}\}$.

Then Neut G_δ -sets are $\{E, F, G, E \cap F\}$. Here $E \cap F \cap G \cap (E \cap F) = G$ and $Ncl(G) = 1_N$. So Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is Neut Volterra space.

Neut α -Open Sets = $\{E, F, G, H, E \cup F, E \cap F, K\}$ and

Neut α -Closed Sets = $\{\bar{E}, \bar{F}, \bar{G}, \bar{H}, \overline{E \cup F}, \overline{E \cap F}\}$.

Then Neut αG_δ -sets are $\{E, F, G, E \cap F\}$. Here $E \cap F \cap G \cap (E \cap F) = G$ and $N\alpha cl(G) = 1_N$. So Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is Neut α -Volterra space.

Proposition 3.9 If $P = \bigcap_{i=1}^N P_i$ where P_i 's are Neut α -dense and Neut αG_δ -sets in a Neut α -Volterra space (X, N_T) then P is not a Neut α -closed set.

Proof: Let $P = \bigcap_{i=1}^N P_i$ where P_i 's are Neut α -dense and Neut αG_δ -sets in (X, N_T) . Since (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra space, we have $N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^N (P_i)) = 1_N$. That is, $N\alpha cl(P) = 1_N$. This implies that $N\alpha cl(P) \neq P$. Hence, P is not a Neut α -closed set in (X, N_T) .

Proposition 3.10 If $B = \bigcup_{i=1}^N B_i$ where B_i 's are Neut α -N.Dense and Neut αF_σ -sets in a Neut α -Volterra space (X, N_T) then B is not a Neut α -open set.

Proof: Let $B = \bigcup_{i=1}^N B_i$ where B_i 's are Neut α dense and Neut αF_σ -sets in (X, N_T) . Since (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra space, we have $N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^N (1 - B_i)) = 1_N$. Since, B_i 's are Neut α N.Dense sets, by the

Proposition 2.4, $1 - B_i$'s are Neut α -dense sets. Since $1 - B = 1 - \bigcup_{i=1}^N B_i = \bigcap_{i=1}^N (1 - B_i)$ we have,

$N\alpha cl(1 - B) = 1_N$. This implies that $N\alpha int(B) = 0_N$. That is $N\alpha int(B) \neq B$. Hence B is not a Neut α -open set in (X, N_T) .

Proposition 3.11: If the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is a Neut irresolvable Neut Baire space, then (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra space, only if every Neut G_δ -sets are Neut dense in (X, N_T) .

Proof: Let P_i 's ($i = 1$ to N) be Neut dense and Neut G_δ -sets in (X, N_T) . Since (X, N_T) is a Neut irresolvable space $Ncl(P_i) = 1_N$ and $Ncl(1 - P_i) \neq 1_N$, implies that $Ncl(N int(P_i)) = 1_N$. Then $1 - Ncl(N int(P_i)) = 0_N$. This implies that $N int(Ncl(1 - P_i)) = 0_N$. Hence $1 - P_i$'s are Neut N.Dense sets in (X, N_T) . Here P_i are Neut G_δ -set in (X, N_T) . Then

$P = \bigcap_{i=1}^\infty P_i$, where P_i 's are open. Then $1 - P = 1 - \bigcap_{i=1}^\infty P_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^\infty 1 - P_i$ which means $1 - P_i$'s are F_σ -sets in (X, N_T) . Hence the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra space.

Proposition 3.12 If the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is a Neut α -irresolvable Neut α -Baire space, then (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra space, only if every Neut αG_δ -sets are Neut α -dense in (X, N_T) .

Proof: Let Q_i 's ($i = 1$ to N) be Neut α -dense and Neut αG_δ -sets in (X, N_T) . Since (X, N_T) is a Neut α -irresolvable space $N\alpha cl(Q_i) = 1_N$ and $N\alpha cl(1 - Q_i) \neq 1_N$ implies that

$N\alpha cl(N\alpha int(Q_i)) = 1_N$. Then $1 - N\alpha cl(N\alpha int(Q_i)) = 0_N$. This implies that

$N\alpha int(N\alpha cl(1 - Q_i)) = 0_N$. Hence $1 - Q_i$'s are Neut α -N.Dense sets in (X, N_T) . Now

$\bigcup_{i=1}^N (1 - Q_i) \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^\infty (1 - Q_i)$. Then we have $N\alpha int(\bigcup_{i=1}^N (1 - Q_i)) \subseteq N\alpha int(\bigcup_{i=1}^\infty (1 - Q_i))$. Since the

Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Baire space, $N\alpha int(\bigcup_{i=1}^\infty (1 - Q_i)) = 0_N$. This implies that

$N\alpha int(\bigcup_{i=1}^N (1 - Q_i)) = 0_N$. Then $N\alpha int(1 - \bigcap_{i=1}^N (Q_i)) = 0_N$ implies that $1 - N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^N (Q_i)) = 0_N$. Then we

have $N\alpha cl(\bigcap_{i=1}^N (Q_i)) = 1_N$. Hence (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra space.

Example 3.5 Let $X = \{p, q, r\}$. Define the Neut set M_1, M_2, P_1, P_2 on X as follows:

$$M_1 = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.4} \right) \right\rangle$$

$$M_2 = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right) \right\rangle$$

$$P_1 = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right) \right\rangle$$

$$P_2 = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.4} \right) \right\rangle$$

Then the family $N_T = \{0_N, 1_N, M_1, M_2, P_1, P_2\}$ is Neut Topology on X . Thus (X, N_T) is a Neut.T.Space. Neut α -Open Sets = $\{M_1, M_2, P_1, P_2\}$ and Neut α -Closed Sets = $\{\bar{M}_1, \bar{M}_2, \bar{P}_1, \bar{P}_2\}$.

Now $N\alpha cl(M_1) = 1_N$, $N\alpha cl(P_2) = 1_N$. Thus M_1 and P_2 are Neut α -dense set in (X, N_T) such that $N\alpha cl(\bar{M}_1) = \bar{M}_1 \neq 1_N$ & $N\alpha cl(\bar{P}_2) = \bar{M}_2 \neq 1_N$. Hence the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called a Neut α -irresolvable.

But Neut αG_δ -set P_1 is not α -dense set in (X, N_T) , since $N\alpha cl(P_1) = \bar{M}_2 \neq 1_N$. So Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is Neut not α -Volterra space.

Proposition 3.13 If P is a Neut αG_δ -set such that $N\alpha cl(P) = 1_N$, in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) then P is a Neut α -residual set in (X, N_T) .

Proof: Let A be a Neut αG_δ -set such that $N\alpha cl(P) = 1_N$ in (X, N_T) . Then by the **Proposition 3.5**, $1 - P$ is a Neut α -first category set in (X, N_T) and hence $1 - (1 - P)$ is a Neut α -residual set in (X, N_T) . That is., P is a Neut α -residual set in (X, N_T) .

Proposition 3.14 If the Neut α -open sets Q_i 's are Neut α -residual in a Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) then (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra space.

Proof: Let Q_i 's be Neut α -residual sets in (X, N_T) and $N\alpha \text{int}(Q_i) = Q_i$. Then $1 - Q_i$'s are α -first category sets in (X, N_T) and $1 - Q = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} 1 - Q_i$, where $1 - Q_i$'s are Neut α -N.Dense in (X, N_T) . That is $N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(1 - Q_i)) = 0_N$. Now $N\alpha \text{int}(Q_i) = Q_i$, implies $N\alpha cl(1 - Q_i) = 1 - Q_i$, this implies $N\alpha \text{int}(N\alpha cl(1 - Q_i)) = N\alpha \text{int}(1 - Q_i)$, so that $N\alpha \text{int}(1 - Q_i) = 0_N$, this implies $N\alpha cl(Q_i) = 1_N$. Thus Q_i 's are Neut α -dense set in (X, N_T) . Now $1 - Q = \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} 1 - Q_i$, gives $Q = \bigcap_{i=1}^{\infty} Q_i$, where Q_i 's are Neut α -open sets in (X, N_T) . Thus Q_i 's are Neut αG_δ -sets in (X, N_T) . Therefore (X, N_T) is a Neut α -Volterra space.

Example 3.5 Let $X = \{p, q, r\}$. Define the Neut set M_1, M_2, P_1, P_2 on X as follows:

$$M_1 = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.4} \right) \right\rangle$$

$$M_2 = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right) \right\rangle$$

$$P_1 = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right) \right\rangle$$

$$P_2 = \left\langle x, \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.5}, \frac{q}{0.5}, \frac{r}{0.5} \right), \left(\frac{p}{0.4}, \frac{q}{0.4}, \frac{r}{0.4} \right) \right\rangle$$

Then the family $N_T = \{0_N, 1_N, M_1, M_2, P_1, P_2\}$ is Neut Topology on X . Thus (X, N_T) is a Neut.T.Space. Neut α -Open Sets = $\{M_1, M_2, P_1, P_2\}$ and Neut α -Closed Sets = $\{\bar{M}_1, \bar{M}_2, \bar{P}_1, \bar{P}_2\}$. Now $N\alpha cl(M_1) = 1_N$, $N\alpha cl(P_2) = 1_N$. Thus M_1 and P_2 are Neut α -dense set in (X, N_T) such that $N\alpha cl(\bar{M}_1) = \bar{M}_1 \neq 1_N$ & $N\alpha cl(\bar{P}_2) = \bar{M}_2 \neq 1_N$. Hence the Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is called a Neut α -irresolvable. But Neut αG_δ -set P_1 is not α -dense set in (X, N_T) , since $N\alpha cl(P_1) = \bar{M}_2 \neq 1_N$. So Neut.T.Space (X, N_T) is Neut not α -Volterra space.

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